

1 . The scheme for determining the softening zone of the coil by one protog of the roller

$R_i = 0.125 - 0.165$ m, $K_c = 0.2$, $h = 0.05$ and $b_p = 0.014$ m, calculations made according to the expression (1) show that the size of the zone of softening of the coil by one protog of the roller is 10 – 11 cm was determined to be

The number of rods to be installed on the reel

We determine the number of rods to be installed on the reel according to the following condition

$$n \geq \frac{2\pi R_i(1+K_c)}{\Delta X} \cdot (2)$$

When this condition is fulfilled, the complete smoothing of the coil is ensured by the roller in the direction of movement.

Taking into account the expression (1.1), the expression (1.2) has the following form:

$$n \geq \frac{2\pi R_i(1+K_c)}{R_i \left\{ \frac{1}{1-K_c} \left[\pi - 2 \arcsin \left(1 - \frac{h}{R_i} \right) \right] - \left[-2 \cos \arcsin \left(1 - \frac{h}{R_i} \right) \right] \right\} + b_p} \cdot (3)$$

By substituting the values of $R_i = 0,125 - 0,165$ m, $K_c = 0,2$, $h = 0,05$ va $b_p = 0,014$ m into this expression, we determine that the number of rods mounted on the reel should be 10 - 12.

The coverage width of the reel

We determine the coverage width of the coil according to the following expression:

$$B = M - 2\Delta, (4)$$

where M is the width of seeded rows (between cotton rows), m;

Δ - the width of the roller protection zone, m.

$M = 60$ cm, $\Delta = 5$ cm [11; pp. 64-65, 13; p. 146] values, we determine that according to expression (4) the coverage width of the coil should be 50 cm.

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